

Study of Fetomaternal Outcome in Pregnancy with Placenta Previa**Santoki Savankumar Jasmatbhai¹, Rathod Tushar Harjibhai², Dashadiya Pavan Jayantilal³, Patel Akash Sureshbhai⁴**¹Resident Doctor, Department of Gynecology, Government Hospital, Gandhidham, Kutch, Gujarat, India²Resident Doctor, Department of Gynecology, Cottage Hospital Vansda, Navsari, Gujarat, India³Resident Doctor, Department of Gynecology, Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel District Hospital Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India⁴Resident Doctor, Department of Gynecology, N.H.L Municipal Medical College, Ellisbridge, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:

Background and Aim: Placenta previa significantly raises the risks for both mother and fetus, primarily due to the increased chances of severe antepartum and postpartum haemorrhage in the mother. It happens because the lower uterine segment does not contract effectively post-delivery. Objectives of the studies were: To estimate proportion of placenta previa at our institute, to evaluate demography, clinical risk factors for placenta previa. to study the clinical presentation, types, management and complications of placenta previa and to evaluate maternal & fetal outcome in patients of placenta previa.

Material and Methods: Present study includes total 52 patients with Placenta Previa admitted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology at tertiary care institute of Gujarat, India. Women's detailed history, gestational age, per abdominal examination, per speculum examination, all routine investigations and USG findings recorded in a predesigned proforma. The women enrolled for the study were observed and maternal and fetal outcome were noted.

Results: It was found that 32.7% of cases of placenta previa were associated with history of previous caesarean section and 17.3% of cases were associated with history of abortion. Majority 47(90.38%) of patients were reported with cephalic presentation. While, amongst the mal-presentation breech (7.7%) was the most. APH and PPH were major complications and were reported in 22 (42.3%) and 24 (46.15%) patients respectively. Maternal mortality occurred in 2 (3.84%) cases. There were 48(92.31%) live births and neonatal mortality occurred in 4 (7.69%) cases.

Conclusion: Placenta previa is life-threatening complications of pregnancy. In placenta previa, APH occurs from placental site, which is located in lower uterine segment. Regular antenatal care helps to detect placenta previa by ultrasound earlier in pregnancy, which is key to prevent the complications of placenta previa.

Keywords: Caesarean Section, Fetomaternal Outcome, Placenta previa, Pregnancy.

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Introduction

Placenta previa (PP) is condition where the placenta is inserted completely or partially into the lower uterine segment, at or after 28 weeks of gestation. [1] In Latin, 'previa' signifies going before, and in this context, the placenta goes before the fetus during passage through the birth canal. It complicates 0.3-0.5% of all pregnancies at term.

Its incidence is increased due to various reasons including wide spread use of ultrasound scanning and increasing rates of caesarean deliveries. It is fatal in 0.03% of patients. Placenta previa is a major cause of antepartum haemorrhage accounting for 35% of all the cause. [2,3] Placenta previa significantly raises the risks for both mother and fetus, primarily due to the increased chances of

severe antepartum and postpartum haemorrhage in the mother. It happens because the lower uterine segment does not contract effectively post-delivery. Additionally, there is a substantially increased likelihood of abnormal placental adherence. With regard to baby, complications such as low birth weight, intrauterine growth restriction and premature birth are more common. [4,5,6]

The key to effectively managing placenta previa is early diagnosis, careful evaluation and timely intervention by appropriate mode of delivery. The maternal and neonatal outcomes can be improved as placenta previa can be diagnosed by antenatal ultrasonography (USG) even before the first episode of bleeding. Additionally, during these

scans, it is crucial to assess for Placenta Accreta Spectrum disorders (PAS) to ensure comprehensive evaluation and management. [7-9]

Objectives of the studies were

- To estimate proportion of placenta previa at our institute.
- To evaluate demography, clinical risk factors for placenta previa.
- To study the clinical presentation, types, management and complications of placenta previa.
- To evaluate maternal & fetal outcome in patients of placenta previa.

Material and Methods

The present study was a prospective observational study done from 1 June 2022 to 31 May 2024 in our tertiary care hospital. This study includes total 52 patients with Placenta Previa admitted in the Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology at our institute after taking informed and written consent.

Inclusion Criteria:

- All cases of placenta previa including placenta accreta, increta and percreta, which were confirmed by USG.
- With gestational age more than 28 weeks.
- Registered, unregistered and referred patients irrespective of parity and fetal viability.

Exclusion Criteria:

- With gestational age less than 28 weeks.
- Patient suffering from bleeding disorder.
- Bleeding from other causes of APH excluding Placenta previa.
- All antenatal women admitted with Placenta Previa and did not delivered at our institute.

The study was based on women admitted in labor ward, in the department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology. The women who fulfilled the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the study. Women's detailed history, gestational age, per abdominal examination, per speculum examination, all routine investigations and USG findings recorded in a predesigned proforma. The women

enrolled for the study were observed and maternal and fetal outcome were noted.

Placenta previa and morbidly adherent placenta require specialized care at advanced medical centers with skilled obstetricians, intensive care units for both mother and baby, anaesthesiologists, neonatal specialists, with availability of blood and components.

Thanks to enhanced healthcare resources, including upgraded facilities, transportation, anaesthesia techniques, and neonatal care units and multidisciplinary approach, the rates of maternal and fetal complications are decreasing worldwide. It is important to make efforts for reduction in the rate of primary caesarean sections because they increase the risk of placenta previa, morbidly adherent placenta, and associated complications in future pregnancies.

Data on characteristics such as age, parity, gestational age at admission, previous caesarean deliveries, uterine anomalies, duration of stay in the hospital, clinical presentation, type of placenta previa at caesarean, malpresentations, hypertension complicating pregnancy, ICU admissions, NICU admission, perinatal mortality were collected.

Statistical analysis

The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2019) and then exported to data editor page of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). Quantitative variables were described as means and standard deviations or median and interquartile range based on their distribution. Qualitative variables were presented as count and percentages. For all tests, confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively.

Results and Discussion

The proportion of placenta previa in present study is 0.52%, while other similar studies showed proportion of placenta previa between 0.6% to 1.37%. In present study 44 (84.6%) patients were registered and 8 (15.4%) were unregistered cases.

Table 1: Age Wise Distribution (N=52)

Age group	Number	Percentage (%)
21 – 25 years	14	26.9%
26 – 30 years	26	50%
31 – 35 years	8	15.4%
36 – 40 years	4	7.7%
Total	52	100%

As shown in Table 1, in present study, 14 (26.9%) patients were from 21- 25 age group, 26 (50%) patients were from 26-30 years age group, 8 (15.4%) patients were from 31-35 years age group

and 4 (7.7%) patient were from 36-40 years age group. Majority (around 70%) of the patients in present study and other similar studies, diagnosed with placenta previa belonged to age group of 21 to

30 years which is the Peak reproductive age group. [10-12] In present study, 23% patients were primigravida and 77% patients were multigravida. In present study and all other similar studies, Multiparous patients have shown the higher

incidence of placenta previa. This is associated with the ageing of vasculature of the uterus. It causes placental hypertrophy and enlargement, which increases the likelihood of the placenta encroaching on lower uterine segment. [11,13-15]

Table 2: Risk factors for Patients of Placenta Previa

Risk factor	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Previous LSCS	17	32.7%
History of D&E	9	17.3%
Previous history of placenta previa	2	3.84%
Tobacco chewing & smoking	5	9.61%
ART	1	1.92%
No identifiable risk factors	26	50%

In present study, 17 (32.7%) patients reported with obstetric history of previous caesarean section, 9 (17.3%) patients reported history of D&E, 2 (3.84%) patients had previous history of placenta previa, 5 (9.61%) patients had history of tobacco chewing & smoking and 1(1.92%) patient had history of ART.

Other similar studies have also reported history of previous caesarean section and previous dilatation and evacuation as a significant risk factor for development of placenta previa. [13-15] Damage to the endometrium or myometrium may be the triggering event for abnormal placental

implantation. The trophoblast can adhere to the uterine scar leading to the placenta covering the cervical os or the placenta invading the walls of the myometrium and giving rise to increased incidence of placenta accreta, increta and percreta.

In present study, type IV placenta previa was seen in 21 (40.38%) patients, type II B in 16 (30.76%) patients, type III in 8 (15.38%) patients, type I in 6 (11.53%) patients and type IIA in 1 (1.92%) patient. Hence, majority of patients 45 (86.84%) had major degree of placenta previa. In most of the other similar studies, majority of the patients had major degree placenta previa. [11,15,16]

Table 3: Relation between Presentation of Fetus and Type of Placenta Previa

Presentation	Type of placenta previa					Total (%)
	I	IIA	IIB	III	IV	
Cephalic	5	1	16	7	18	47 (90.38%)
Breech	1	0	0	1	2	4 (7.7%)
Transverse lie	0	0	0	0	1	1 (1.92%)
Total	6	1	16	8	21	52 (100%)
Percentage (%)	11.53%	1.92%	30.76%	15.38%	40.38%	100%

As shown in Table 3, in present study, cephalic presentation was found in 47 (90.38%) patients of placenta previa. Presentation was breech in 4 (7.7%) patients and transverse lie in 1 (1.92%). Incidence of malpresentation is higher in type III and type IV of placenta previa because the placenta occupies the lower uterine segment and prematurity also hinders with normal vertex presentation which increases the incidence of malpresentation.

In present study, 8 (15.38%) patients were delivered before 34 weeks, 12 (23.07%) patients were delivered between 34-37 weeks and 32

(61.54%) were delivered after 37 weeks. Hence, preterm delivery rate in present study is relatively higher (38.46%). in other similar studies like G D Maiti et al and P Ramasamy et al, the incidences of pre term delivery (<37 weeks) 37.7% and 44% respectively. [11,14]

In present study, majority of patients presented with no abdominal pain 36 (69.23%). Usually, abdominal pain is absent in placenta previa unless the patient is in labor. Majority of patients who had abdominal pain in our study were near term or had preterm labor pain.

Table 4: Mode of Delivery (N=52)

Mode of Delivery	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Caesarean Section	Emergency	40
	Elective	11
Vaginal Delivery	1	1.92%
Total	52	100%

As shown in Table 4, caesarean section was performed in 51 (98.08%) and out of these 40(76.92%) patients were taken for emergency Caesarean Section and 11 (21.16%) patients were taken for elective Caesarean Section.

Normal vaginal delivery occurred in one patient having minor degree of placenta previa who came in active stage of labor. Other similar studies have reported that cesarean section was performed in

majority of patients. [11,13,14] Vaginal delivery can be attempted in minor degree of placenta previa.

However, presence of bleeding episodes and unfavorable cervix may necessitate timely caesarean section. Hence, caesarean section remains gold standard for management of placenta previa.

Table 5: Complications and Relation to Degree of Placenta Previa

Complications		Minor (N=7)	Major (N=45)	Total (N=52)	Percentage (%)
Antepartum	APH	2 (28.57%)	20 (44.44%)	22	42.3%
Intra Operative	Adherent placenta	Placenta Accreta	1	2	3.84%
		Placenta Inrcreta	1		
	Urinary Bladder Injury	0	2	2	3.84%
Post-Partum	PPH	2 (28.57%)	22 (48.88%)	24	46.15%
	DIC	0	2	2	3.84%
	Renal Failure	0	1	1	1.92%
	Fever	0	2	2	3.84%
	Wound gap	1	0	1	1.92%
	Maternal Death	0	2	2	3.84%

As shown in Table 5, in present study, antepartum haemorrhage occurred in 22 (42.3%), out of these minor and major placenta previa was present in 2 and 20 patients respectively. It shows that, chances of APH are higher in major degree (44.44%) than in minor degree (28.57%). Intra operatively in 2 patients of major type of placenta previa, adherent placenta was found. Obstetric hysterectomy was required in those cases. On histopathological examination of specimens of these two obstetric hysterectomies, placenta accreta and placenta increta were reported. Urinary bladder injury occurred in 2 (3.84%) patients, which was repaired.

PPH occurred in 24 (46.15%) patients, chances of PPH are higher in major degree (48.88%) than in minor degree (28.57%). DIC, Renal failure was found in 2 (3.84%) and 1(1.92%) respectively. There were 2 (3.84%) patients who had reported fever on day 3-4 of CS, which was managed medically, whereas 1 (1.92%) patient reported wound gap on day 10 of CS that was managed by re-suturing. Hence, in present study, major complications were APH (42.3%) and PPH (46.15%). Maternal mortality occurred in 2 (3.84%) patients. other similar studies also have reported APH and PPH as major complications in placenta previa. [13,14,16] APH in placenta previa is due to stretching and dilatation of lower uterine segment, placenta is sheared off from the uterine wall leading to opening of utero placental sinuses. Chances of postpartum hemorrhage is more common in patients of placenta previa due to focal atony of the lower uterine segment where the placenta was implanted. 24 (46.15%) patients had developed PPH, as there was excessive bleeding

from sinuses. Medical management was done in form of uterotonics and pressure was applied for hemostasis in all patients. Complete hemostasis was achieved by medical management and/or surgical management. Bilateral uterine artery ligation (BLUAL) was performed in 20 (38.46%) and uterine packing was done in 2 (3.84%). BLUAL along with uterine packing and B-Lynch suture was required in 1 (1.92%) each. Obstetric hysterectomy was required in 4 patients when all other modalities for management of PPH failed and in 2 patients of adherent placenta. In all patients of PPH, hypovolemia was corrected by crystalloid and blood transfusion. In present study, 35 (67.3%) patients required transfusion of blood and blood components. in present study and other similar studies have reported BLUAL and obstetric hysterectomy and blood transfusion along with medical management as lifesaving modalities of management in patients of placenta previa.

A chi-square test was performed to examine the relation between degree of placenta previa and numbers of patients with blood transfusion. The relation between these variables was significant, ($p < 0.05$), which proves that, numbers of patients requiring blood transfusion are higher in major degree placenta previa. In present study, maternal mortality occurred in two (3.84%) cases. One due to PPH and patient could not be saved despite obstetric hysterectomy and other one due to DIC which ultimately led to multiple organ failure and mortality. In other similar studies the maternal mortality rate in cases of placenta previa varies from 0.9% to 7%. [11,13,17,18] In present study, majority of patients were registered patients who

were taking regular antenatal care. Early diagnosis and prompt management of complications at tertiary care hospital helps to decrease maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality. In present study, 48 (92.31%) neonates were alive. In other similar

studies, live birth rate varies from 65.7% to 92%. In present study, neonatal death occurred in 4 (7.69%) cases due to preterm and prematurity followed by early onset septicemia and difficulty in maintaining saturation of preterm babies.

Table 6: NICU Admission

NICU Admission	No. of babies		Total
	Survived	Expired	
No	37	0	37 (71.15%)
Yes	11	4	15 (28.85%)
Total	48	4	52 (100%)

As shown in Table 6, Out of 52 babies of placenta previa, 48 babies survived. 15 (28.85%) babies required NICU care, of which 4 (7.69%) died and

11 (21.15%) babies survived and discharged. There were 37 (71.15%) babies who did not require NICU admission.

Table 7: Relationship of Gestational Age, Baby Weight and Fetal outcome

Birth Weight	Gestational age in weeks and fetal outcome						Number (%)
	Alive			Neonatal Death			
	28-34	34-37	>37	28-34	34-37	>37	Total
<1 kg	0	0	0	1	0	0	1(1.92%)
1 – 1.5 kg	0	0	0	2	0	0	2(3.84%)
1.6 – 2 kg	3	2	0	1	0	0	6(11.54%)
2.1 – 2.5 kg	1	7	11	0	0	0	19(36.54%)
>2.5 kg	0	3	21	0	0	0	24(46.16%)
Total	4	12	32	4	0	0	52(100%)

As shown in Table 7, in our study, 4 neonatal mortalities reported. Out of which 1 baby had weight <1 kg and 2 babies had birth weight between 1-1.5kg at the time of delivery while 1 baby had birth weight 1.8 kg. All 4 babies were preterm with 28-34 weeks of gestation. 48 live births recorded, out of which 5 babies weighed below 2 kg and 43 babies weighed >2kg and all survived. Majority 32 (61.54%) babies delivered at full term while 20 (38.46%) babies reported preterm.

Hence, in present study perinatal mortality rate was 7.69%. A chi-square test was performed to examine the relation between birthweight and neonatal death. The relation between these variables was significant, ($p < 0.05$), which proves that chances of neonatal deaths are higher in babies with lower birthweight. In present study, out of 50 patients who were discharged from hospital successfully, 8 (16%) patients had hospital stay of less than 7 days, 26 (52%) patients had hospital stay of 7-10 days while 16(32%) patients had hospital stay of more than 10 days. This indicates patients with placenta previa requires longer hospital stay.

Conclusion

Placenta previa is life-threatening complications of pregnancy. In placenta previa, APH occurs from placental site, which is located in lower uterine segment. Regular antenatal care helps to detect placenta previa by ultrasound earlier in pregnancy,

which is key to prevent the complications of placenta previa. This early diagnosis will help in proper counselling and educating the patients about the condition, improvement in Hb level and importance of delivery at tertiary care centre.

It also helps the obstetrician in planning a better management of such patients.

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